

Biochar improves the soil sponge and habitat functions of three Portuguese pasture soils according to their vulnerability to hardsetting

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Abstract

Purpose: Hardsetting soils are characterized by poor soil structure, where slumping along the soil profile during the drying phase results in limited water infiltration, restricted root development and reduced productivity in Mediterranean pasture systems. These hardsetting properties are subsequently (partially) reversed during the wetting phase, making hardsetting a transient soil property that affects the soil sponge and habitat functions. This study aimed to evaluate whether wood-derived biochar improves key properties of Portuguese pasture soils and alleviates symptoms of hardsetting.

Methods: Soils that ranged from low to high to very high vulnerability to hardsetting, from three Portuguese pastures, were collected, air-dried, sieved, mixed to biochar concentrations (0, 1.5, 3, 6 and 10 %; w/w), packed into columns and incubated (n=3). All treatments underwent 4 wetting-drying cycles, during which indicators that underpin the soil habitat and soil sponge functions were monitored.

Results: The findings show that biochar not only enhanced soil structure by reducing bulk density (-36% at 10% biochar), but apparently also by reducing slumping, which had a several times greater effect on soil unsaturated hydraulic conductivity (K) (increased 60-500% already at 1.5% biochar and 246-2500% at 10%). Biochar amendments also significantly increased MWHC (up to +92 % at 10% biochar) and decreased penetration resistance (37-51%).

Conclusions: In conclusion, the “soil sponge” and “habitat” functions may be substantially improved by biochar amendment, although potentially at different biochar concentrations and depending on the soil’s vulnerability to hardsetting, with potential agronomic and ecological benefits for Mediterranean pastures.

Keywords: Soil amendment, hydraulic conductivity, bulk density, aggregation, soil compaction, penetration resistance.

38 **1. Introduction**

39 Soil degradation is among the most pressing global environmental challenges, threatening
40 agricultural productivity, ecosystem services, and biodiversity (European Commission, 2021). In
41 Mediterranean regions, where fragile soils are exposed to alternating drought and intense rainfall and where
42 climate change is intensifying both drying trends and extreme precipitation events (Tomaz et al. 2025),
43 degradation impacts the ability of soils to infiltrate, retain and release water, aka soil sponge function
44 (Gholamahmadi et al. 2025), through soil organic matter decline, compaction, salinization, surface
45 crusting, and, particularly for coarse-textured soils, hardsetting by slumping, (Mullins et al. 1990; Verheijen
46 et al. 2009). These processes reduce infiltration, increase erosion risk, impede seedling emergence and, root
47 elongation and compromise other soil functions such as carbon storage and nutrient cycling thereby making
48 them a major agronomic constraint in Mediterranean pastures and rainfed systems. This soil degradation
49 also impacts the soil habitat function, which, according to De Deyn and Kooistra (2021), refers to the soil's
50 capacity to support a diverse and dynamic biological community, causing the decline of soil-dependent
51 fauna and pollinator communities (Potts et al. 2005; Harmon-Threatt, 2020). Restoring the structural and
52 hydrological integrity of these soils is, therefore, fundamental not only for agricultural resilience, but also
53 for sustaining ecosystem services essential to biodiversity and food security.

54 Hardsetting arises from multiple interacting mechanisms and, unlike crusting does not require an
55 overburden (Mullins et al. 1990; Bresson and Moran, 2004). Upon wetting, aggregates slake and disperse
56 due to low electrolyte concentration and insufficient organic binding agents. Hardsetting occurs as the soil
57 dries, when fine particles do not flocculate and re-arrange, welding into dense, structureless masses
58 (Daniels, 2012). Hardsetting can be accompanied by compaction (loss of macroporosity), although some
59 authors have observed hardsetting by aggregate coalescence or aggregate welding, where minimal
60 compaction occurs (Kwaad and Muecher, 1994). The process is exacerbated by organic matter depletion,
61 clay eluviation, and repeated wet-dry cycles (Bresson and Moran, 2004). The strong drying part of the
62 wetting-drying cycles of the Mediterranean climate, predisposes surface and potentially, subsurface
63 horizons to hardsetting, which is eventually reversed during the wetting phase, making it a transient soil
64 property. Hardsetting soils form structureless, massive surface horizons with poor friability and infiltration
65 (Mullins et al. 1990). A review about hardsetting soils in the EU concluded: “slumping is likely to be rather
66 common in most light-textured soils of Europe. It is surprising that only a few papers devoted to slumping
67 in Europe have been published in international soil science journals” (Bresson et al. 2006). They also

68 observed that sandy loam soils with low organic matter may be particularly vulnerable to hardsetting. Of
69 the Mediterranean countries in the EU, Portugal has the greatest proportion of coarse-textured soil and the
70 lowest average soil organic matter content (Aksoy et al. 2016), reducing the available water capacity
71 (Ballabio et al. 2016), making Portuguese soil particularly vulnerable to hardsetting.

72 Biochar, a stable, carbon-rich byproduct of biomass pyrolysis can persist for decades and even
73 hundreds of years, modifies pore geometry, and improves soil sponge function (Verheijen et al. 2019;
74 Jeffery et al. 2017). Its high surface area and porosity facilitate water retention and microbial colonization,
75 while its alkaline nature can ameliorate soil acidity. Despite global progress, research on biochar as a
76 physical soil conditioner in hardsetting soils specifically, remains scarce. Most European studies have
77 focused on nutrient dynamics or greenhouse gas emissions, leaving soil structural and hydrological impacts
78 underexplored (Verheijen et al. 2019). Soil physical quality is a fundamental driver of pollinator habitat
79 function. By regulating soil moisture and nutrient availability, healthy soils influence floral abundance as
80 well as nectar and pollen production, while also determining the suitability of the soil matrix for ground-
81 nesting bees (Potts et al. 2005; Harmon-Threatt, 2020). However, few studies have explicitly linked
82 improvements in soil physical quality to ecological functions, particularly pollinator habitat suitability for
83 nesting. Compacted or crusted and surface welded soils hinder nest excavation and moisture regulation,
84 negatively affecting pollinator diversity and abundance. Pollinators are vital to ecosystem functioning:
85 about 88% of flowering plant species and three-quarters of global food crops rely on or benefit from animal-
86 mediated pollination (Ollerton et al. 2011; Klein et al. 2017). Bees, both managed and wild, are the primary
87 pollinators, accounting for roughly half of the global economic value of pollination (Garibaldi et al. 2013;
88 Kleijn et al. 2015). 75% of wild bees are ground-nesting species that excavate burrows, creating macropores
89 that improve water flow, gas exchange, and soil structure (Cane and Neff, 2011; Danforth et al. 2019;
90 Tschanz et al. 2023). Their activity can displace 5–27 Mg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ of soil, surpassing many other soil
91 bioturbators such as ants or termites (Cane, 2003; Watanabe, 1998). Understanding how amendments like
92 biochar influence soil properties important for nesting and moisture regulation is therefore critical for
93 linking soil restoration with pollinator habitat improvement.

94 Biochar's impact on soil porosity can enhance the soil sponge function, i.e. water infiltration and
95 retention (Edeh et al. 2020; Gholamahmadi et al. 2023), but not necessarily soil aggregation, at least not
96 directly (Zhou et al. 2018). If biochar reduces the vulnerability to hardsetting, directly or indirectly, it may
97 contribute more to improving the soil sponge and soil habitat functions than may be apparent from biochar

108 effects on bulk density or aggregation alone. Therefore, the objective of this study was to evaluate the
109 effects of wood-derived biochar on indicators of the soil sponge and habitat functions for soils with varying
110 vulnerability to hardsetting. The study specifically focused on potential trade-offs between these functions
111 in a range of biochar concentrations.

112 **2. Materials and Methods**

113 **2.1 Study sites, soil and biochar properties**

114 Soils were collected from three Portuguese pasture sites managed as Sown Biodiverse Pastures
115 (SBP) and monitored by Terraprima. SPBs are oversown with legumes, grasses, and forbs, established
116 annually following summer drought, with the start of the autumn rains (AFJ, 2010; Teixeira et al. 2015).
117 Sampling took place during January 2023. After removing the root mat of approximately 3 cm, the soil was
118 sampled to approximately 12 cm depth and transported to the lab in the Department of Environment and
119 Planning. The soils were selected based on their degree of vulnerability to hardsetting, i.e. based on soil
120 texture and SOM contents (Bresson et al. 2006). The most vulnerable to hardsetting was a Sandy Loam
121 with Low SOM content (SL-L) from Herdade de Pecena, followed by a Sandy Loam with High SOM
122 content (SL-H) from Quinta da França, and finally a Sandy Clay Loam with high SOM content (SCL-H)
123 from Herdade dos Padres. Climatic and soil characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

124 Biochar was acquired from Swiss Biochar GmbH (Switzerland), produced through slow pyrolysis
125 at a peak temperature of 620°C using pine wood chip feedstock, with an ash content of 18.6% and a pH of
126 10.1. The full physicochemical characterisation of biochar is reported by Prodana et al. (2019). Briefly, the
127 particle size distribution was as follows: 4% of particles were smaller than 0.1 mm, 25% ranged from 0.1
128 to 0.5 mm, 34% from 0.5 to 2 mm, and 37% were larger than 2 mm. Both the soil and the biochar were
129 determined as wettable by a modified version (Verheijen et al. 2007) of the Water Drop Penetration Time
130 (WDPT) test (Van't Woudt, 1959), see supplement SI.1.

131 **2.2 Experimental design**

132 To address the research objectives, a controlled laboratory column experiment was selected to
133 isolate the physical effects of biochar on soil structure and hydrological properties under standardized
134 conditions. The experiment followed a completely randomized design (CRD) with three soil types with
135 varying vulnerabilities to hardsetting (Table 1), i.e. lower clay and soil organic matter contents indicate

126 higher vulnerability. The treatments consisted of five biochar concentrations (0, 1.5, 3, 6, and 10% w/w),
127 each replicated three times, resulting in a total of 45 experimental units. The experimental work was carried
128 out between January and May 2023

129 The collected soil was passed over a 4 mm sieve, oven-dried and weighed to calculate how much
130 water should be added to reach the target moisture content for incubation of 60% volumetric maximum
131 water holding capacity (MWHC). A representative biochar sample was taken and its gravimetric moisture
132 content was determined by oven-drying at 105°C for 24 hours. Biochar was sieved into its main particle
133 size categories: > 2 mm, 2-0.05mm, 0.09-0.05mm, <0.05mm, so each treatment mixture contains a
134 representative relative proportion of each particle size. The biochar was then moistened with distilled water
135 until reaching at least 20% (gravimetric) moisture content before being mixed with soil. Biochar was then
136 homogeneously mixed with moist soil at the target treatment gravimetric (w/w) concentrations (0%, 1.5%,
137 3%, 6%, 10%).

138 Gravimetric water content of the soil-biochar mixtures was then adjusted to 10%, using
139 demineralised water to simulate rainwater. The soil-biochar mixtures were then incubated for 28 days at
140 20°C ± 2°C in transparent plastic bags. To stop the incubation the mixtures were placed in a fridge at 4°C
141 until used. After the incubation period, it was noticed that the SL-L 3% mixture had not been wetted before
142 starting the incubation and thus was incubated at a much lower moisture content. This visibly changed the
143 properties of the mixture, with ramifications for the results, as discussed in the discussion section.

144 The incubated mixtures were packed in PVC columns according to the method of Verheijen et al.
145 (2019). In short, the tubes were 12.5 cm in height with an inner diameter of 5.8 cm, covered by a cotton
146 mesh at the bottom, allowing free drainage. Before filling the PVC columns, the incubated mixtures were
147 homogenized, and the largest aggregates were crushed by hand. For each treatment, 3 PVC columns were
148 filled up to approximately 10 cm in height. They were packed by a coffee stamper, only using the weight
149 of the coffee stamper.

150 **2.3 Soil sponge function indicators**

151 2.3.1 Maximum water holding capacity (MWHC)

152 The maximum water holding capacity (MWHC), aka gravity-drained equilibrium moisture content
153 (Laird et al. 2010), was determined as described by Veihmeyer and Hendrickson (1949), with adaptations

154 used in Verheijen et al (2019). Soil columns were wetted from the bottom by placing them in a plastic crate
155 and adding tap water until the level exceeded the soil surface. After ponding, columns were set on a grid to
156 drain freely for 24 h or until drainage stopped. During drainage, aluminium foil covered the columns to
157 limit evaporation and avoid vacuum formation. Columns were then weighed, oven-dried at 105 °C for 24
158 h, and reweighed to determine dry weight. Equation 1 was then used to calculate gravimetric MWHC.

$$159 \quad \text{Gravimetric soil water content (\%)} = \frac{M_{\text{water}}}{M_{\text{soil}}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

160 Where M_{water} is the mass of water in grams and M_{soil} is the mass of the oven-dry soil in grams.

161 2.3.2 Unsaturated hydraulic conductivity by infiltrometer

162 Unsaturated hydraulic conductivity was measured during the column experiment using a mini disk
163 infiltrometer (MDI; Decagon Devices, 2006). The instrument consists of a transparent tube divided into
164 an upper chamber controlling pressure head and a lower chamber serving as a water reservoir, fitted at the
165 base with a porous ceramic disk in contact with the soil surface. The pressure head was adjustable
166 between -0.5 cm and -7 cm. Before testing, all samples were air-dried with fan assistance until control
167 soils reached 5–10 % moisture, resulting in gravimetric contents of 4–30 % across mixtures. To ensure
168 proper contact with the ceramic disk, the surface 2 mm of each sample was gently loosened with a spoon
169 and repacked using a coffee stamper. The infiltrometer was filled with tap water, and the water level was
170 recorded every 20 s for 8 min with a stopwatch, producing 24 measurements per sample. The initial
171 pressure head of -5 cm was reduced to -2 cm after several columns exhibited limited infiltration. After
172 each test, the ceramic disk was rinsed with tap water. The full set of 45 columns was measured over two
173 consecutive days. Unsaturated hydraulic conductivity (K) was calculated from the infiltration data
174 following the method of Zhang (1997).

175 For MDI infiltration measurements, two control replicates of SL-H and one control replicate of
176 SL-L returned negative K values, as well as one replicate from the 1.5% biochar treatment of SL-L. Since
177 negative infiltration is not physically meaningful, these values were converted to 0 in order to proceed with
178 the analysis. The cumulative infiltration was plotted against time using equation 2:

$$179 \quad I = C1 + C2 \sqrt{t} \quad (2)$$

180 Where I represents the cumulative infiltration, $C1$ a parameter related to hydraulic conductivity, $C2$ a
181 parameter related to soil sorptivity and t the time. The unsaturated hydraulic conductivity is then
182 calculated via equation 3:

$$183 \quad K = C1A \quad (3)$$

184 Where $C1$ represents the slope of the curve of the cumulative infiltration vs the square root of time and A
185 is a value relating the Van Genuchten parameters for a given soil type to the suction head of the
186 infiltrometer and the radius of the infiltrometer disk. A is computed using equation 4:

$$187 \quad A = \frac{11.65(n^{0.1} - 1) \exp [7.5(n - 1.9)\alpha h_o]}{(\alpha r_o)^{0.91}} \quad (4)$$

188 In which α and n are the Van Genuchten parameters, h_o the suction of the infiltrometer and r_o the radius
189 of the infiltrometer.

190 2.3.3 Time to saturation and drainage

191 For third and fourth wetting-drying cycles, the time that it took for samples to show ponding during the
192 wetting phase and stop ponding during the drying phase was recorded. The time, after immersion of the
193 tube, at which the soil surface was completely covered with water was noted as “time to ponding”. The
194 ponded columns were left in the water for 15–30 minutes and then placed on a grid to drain, the time at
195 which this was done was noted as the starting time of drainage. The moment when the surface of a mixture
196 had lost any ponding water was then also noted as “time to drainage”.

197 2.4 Soil habitat function indicators

198 2.4.1 Dry Bulk Density (BDdry)

199 BDdry was determined at the beginning and end of the column experiment. All samples were air-
200 dried for one week, oven-dried at 105°C for 24 h, cooled in desiccators, and weighed. Column height was
201 measured after the penetration resistance test (see 2.4.2) to calculate soil volume, from which BDc4 was
202 derived as the ratio of oven-dry mass to soil volume, using equation 5.

$$203 \quad BD_{dry} (g \text{ cm}^{-3}) = \frac{\text{Dry soilmass}}{\text{Total volume}} \quad (5)$$

204

205 2.4.2 Penetration Resistance

206 Penetration resistance was measured on all 45 column samples at the end of the column
207 experiment, following 48 h of air-drying (when soil moisture contents ranged from 5–20%). Measurements
208 were taken using a pocket penetrometer (Eijkelkamp, n.a.) consisting of a metal pin attached to a calibrated
209 spring, where applied force is indicated by a slip ring on the scale. The procedure was standardized by
210 inserting the full pin length (2.2 cm) once for each sample.

211 2.4.3 Sodium Adsorption Ratio

212 Sodium Adsorption Ratio (SAR) was determined following the procedure of Abrol et al. (2016),
213 with modified preparatory steps to obtain a clear soil leachate. The 45 air-dried samples previously used
214 for aggregate size distribution were remixed and sieved to <2 mm. Each 30 g subsample was combined
215 with 45 mL of demineralized water in a square plastic container and shaken mechanically for 1 h at 270
216 rpm. The suspensions were centrifuged for 10 min at 4,000 rpm, and the supernatant was collected and
217 sequentially filtered, first through paper and then a finer membrane filter, using a vacuum pump. Na, Ca,
218 and Mg concentrations were measured with a flame atomic absorption spectrometer (FAAS). SAR was
219 then calculated according to equation 6:

220
$$SAR = \frac{[Na^+]}{\sqrt{\frac{[Ca^{2+}] + [Mg^{2+}]}{2}}} \quad (6)$$

221 2.4.4 Aggregate Size Distribution

222 The aggregate size distribution was determined by calculating the mean weight diameter (MWD;
223 Chaney and Swift, 1984). From each of the 15 incubated mixtures, 250 grams of soil was air-dried and
224 subsequently divided in 3 replicates. This resulted in 45 samples with a weight of 65 – 85 grams each. The
225 samples were automatically sieved over a stack of sieves with mesh sizes 4, 2, 1, 0.5 and 0.25 mm at 40
226 osc/min for 2 minutes. After sieving the different fractions were collected and weighed, resulting in the
227 following 6 aggregate size fractions: >4, 4-2, 2-1, 1-0.5, 0.5-0.25 and <0.25 mm.

228 The MWD (mm) was calculated from the dry sieving using the following equation 7 (Bavel, 1950):

229
$$MWD = \sum_{i=1}^n \bar{X}_i W_i \quad (7)$$

230 Where \bar{X}_i is the mean diameter of each size class (mm), W_i is the mass proportion of each size class, and n
231 is the number of size classes over the bulk soil.

232 **2.5 Data analysis**

233 All numerical processing and descriptive statistics were performed in Microsoft Excel (Microsoft
234 Corporation, USA). Replicate values ($n = 3$) for each soil–biochar treatment were used to calculate
235 arithmetic means, standard deviations and coefficients of variation. Excel was also used to construct tables
236 and figures. SAR, MWD, and PR were analyzed by two-way Anova with interaction between soil types
237 and biochar concentrations. Field capacity, MDI, bulk density, time to ponding, and time to lose ponding
238 were analyzed with linear mixed effects (LME) models by restricted maximum likelihood with three-way
239 interaction between soil type, biochar concentration, and cycle in fixed effects structure, and with pots
240 (replicates) in random effect structure to account for the repeated measurements. Afterwards, Anova type
241 3 (type III sum of squares) was fitted on each LME model as indication of the general effects of soil types,
242 concentration rates, and cycles. For all the variables, Tukey post-hoc tests were used for pairwise-
243 comparisons. All the analyses were made in R; two-way Anova's with "stats", LME models with "lme4"
244 and "lmerTest", type 3 Anovas with "car", and pairwise comparisons with "emmeans" package. The model
245 outputs are available in Supplementary information SI.2. One replicate of the 1.5% biochar treatment for
246 SL-L soil was lost after the first drainage cycle and excluded from analyses involving MWHC, drainage
247 time, saturation time, penetration resistance and bulk density for the fourth cycle. All replicates from SL-L
248 0% biochar treatment, and one replicate from SL-H 0% biochar treatment took so long to saturate that that
249 the exact time could not be measured. For all replicates of SL-L 0% and 1.5% treatments, plus SL-H 0%
250 biochar treatment the time to drainage was also too long to record the exact time. For these replicates
251 minimum values of the range were selected to be used in statistical analysis.

252 **3. Results**

253 **3.1 Indicators of hydraulic conductivity**

254 Figure 1a and 1b show that biochar caused very large reductions in the time until
255 saturation/drainage measured during the third saturation and drainage cycle, mostly at 1.5% and 3%
256 biochar. Time to saturation shows a power decay relationship with increasing biochar concentration, while
257 time to drainage shows a threshold relationship with >99% of the decrease occurring at 3% biochar for the

258 sandy loam soils and at 1.5% biochar for the SCL-H soil. In the absence of biochar, the sandy loam soils
259 drained and saturated 3-4 times slower than the SCL-H soil. Figure 1c shows that biochar strongly increased
260 hydraulic conductivity (K) up to 3% biochar concentration, after which the increase in K decelerated for
261 the SL-H soil, while it increased strongly for the SCL-H soil. The SL-L soil showed the weakest increase
262 in K as a more or less linear relationship. At the highest biochar concentration (10%), the SCL-H soil had
263 a K value that was 2-3 times greater than for the two sandy loam soils. Figures 1d-f, illustrate the change
264 in MWHC over the four saturation and drainage cycles. In all soils, MWHC decreases gradually until cycle
265 3. For SCL-H this decreases levels off at the fourth cycle, while SL-H and SL-L see a slight increase in
266 MWHC values, all differences between the first to the third and fourth cycles in all soils are significant (p
267 < 0.001). MWHC showed significant differences between first and second cycles for SL-L 3, 6 and 10%
268 biochar treatments. SCL-H had significant differences between first and second cycles, first and third and,
269 between first and fourth cycles ($p < 0.01$). SL-H shows significant differences in between first to second,
270 third and fourth cycles, except for 10% biochar treatment, $p < 0.01$ and $p = 0.11$ respectively. None of the
271 soils had significant differences between 0-1.5% and 1.5 - 3% treatments.

272

273 **Fig. 1** Hydraulic behavior of three pasture soils. Panel (a) shows the time to drainage and panel (b) the time
 274 to saturation, both recorded during the third saturation and drainage cycle. Panel (c) presents unsaturated
 275 hydraulic conductivity (K) measured at the beginning of the first saturation cycle; Panels (d), (e), and (f)
 276 display the maximum water holding capacity (MWHC) across four consecutive wetting and drainage
 277 cycles. Error bars represent standard deviations. Asterisks in Panels (a) and (b) indicate cases where
 278 saturation or drainage extended overnight, and minimum values were used

279

280 3.2 Indicators of Soil Structure

281 Figure 2a shows the dose-response curve for the MWD. The two sandy loam soils show a strong
 282 decrease in MWD from the control to 3% biochar ($p < 0.0001$), without any significant change at higher
 283 biochar concentrations. SCL-H shows a more gradual decrease in MWD with increasing biochar

284 concentration. Figure 2b shows the percentage of relative weight of microaggregate fraction, there is a
285 slight increase in the relative weight of the microaggregate fraction with increasing biochar content. The
286 asterisk signals a value obtained for the 3% treatment where the soils incubation was not performed at the
287 beginning of the experiment. Figure 2c shows the effect of increasing biochar concentrations on the soil
288 SAR. In the absence of biochar (0%), SCL-H exhibited the highest SAR (0.57), followed by SL-L (0.37)
289 and SL-H (0.20). The two sandy loam soils did not show any significant change in SAR, while the sandy
290 clay loam soil showed a linear decline, with increasing biochar concentrations, but without significance.
291 Figure 2d shows the effect of biochar on BD in the first cycle (BDc1) and effect of biochar on BDc4 With
292 increasing biochar concentrations, the BDc1 of all soils decreases in a linear pattern, with approximately
293 3.7% decrease for every percent increase in biochar concentration and for BDc4 it can be seen that with
294 increasing biochar concentrations, the BDc4 of all soils decreases in a linear pattern, with approximately
295 3.6% decrease for every percent increase in biochar concentration. SL-L showed no significant differences
296 between first and fourth cycles for all treatments, SL-H showed significant differences between first and
297 fourth cycles for all treatments ($p < 0.01$) except for 6% biochar treatments with $p = 0.8651$ respectively.
298 SCL-H had significant differences between cycle 1 and cycle 4 for all treatments ($p < 0.01$). Differences
299 between treatments in each soil were all significant ($p < 0.001$) except between 1.5 and 3 % treatments for
300 all soils and cycles, did not find significant differences between 3% and 6 % for SCL-H first and second
301 cycles, as for SL-H second cycle between 3 and 6% treatments no significant differences were found.
302 Figure 2e shows the effect of biochar concentration on the soil's penetration resistance. The two sandy loam
303 soils show a more or less gradual decrease in PR with increasing biochar, with significant differences
304 between 0-10% treatments, with significantly higher PR values for the SL-L at higher biochar
305 concentrations (6% and 10%).
306 SCL-H shows a 36% decrease in PR between the control and 1.5% biochar mixture, though it is not
307 significant, with $p = 0.23$, but no further reductions at higher biochar concentrations. Figure 2f shows the
308 relationships between BDc4 and PR for the 3 soils, where SCL-H shows no increase in PR until 10%
309 biochar, while the 2 sandy loam soils show a positive relation that is somewhat stronger for the one with
310 more organic matter, i.e. SL-H.

311

312 **Fig. 2** Indicators of soil structure across three pasture soils. Panel (a) presents the mean weight diameter
 313 (MWD); Panel (b) displays the weight of the microaggregate fraction in percentage, the asterisk signals a
 314 value obtained for the 3% treatment where the soils incubation was not performed at the beginning of the
 315 experiment; Panel (c) shows the Sodium Adsorption Ratio (SAR); Panel (d) shows dry bulk density at
 316 cycle 1 (BDc1) and cycle 4 (BDc4); Panel (e) presents penetration resistance (PR); and Panel (f)
 317 represents a regression between PR and BDc4. Error bars represent standard deviations for each treatment
 318 and soil. Asterisk in Panel (b) indicates a mixture that was not incubated

319 **4. Discussion**

320 The major finding from this study was that biochar very strongly improved soil hydrology, while soil
 321 structure was only improved moderately. The greater the limitations of the soil, expressed as the

322 vulnerability to hardsetting (Table 1), the greater the improvements that biochar provided to soil hydrology,
323 while the improvements in soil structure were mostly independent of the vulnerability to hardsetting.

324 The BD values of the control soils after the first cycle ranged from 1.16-1.42 g cm⁻³, and 1.29-1.49 g cm⁻¹
325 after three more cycles. This means that wetting-drying cycles alone, i.e. without any soil loading, brought
326 the BDs within 0.10-0.15 g cm⁻³ of field conditions. Biochar addition reduced the BD by 3.6% for every
327 percent increase in biochar concentration, which is consistent with what meta-analyses have found (Omondi
328 et al. 2016; Razzaghi et al. 2020), and most likely due to a straightforward dilution effect, because unlike
329 findings from meta-analyses, biochar consistently reduced the MWD. Figure 2b shows that biochar
330 consistently increased the microaggregates (<0.25 mm), and it also shows how incubation conditions are
331 essential, for the one sample that was not wetted prior to incubation (SL-L 3% biochar) had a 3 times greater
332 proportion of microaggregates. Soil amendments generally cause an increase in MWD (Basset et al. 2023),
333 which is then posited to cause increased hydraulic conductivity, although Zhou et al. (2018) found that for
334 a sandy loam soil, maize feedstock biochar did not change the proportion of macroaggregates or aggregate
335 stability, but did enhance the hydraulic conductivity. Of the hydrological variables, the strongest biochar
336 effects were observed for “time to ponding” and “time to drainage” with varying effect sizes but similar
337 patterns for the tree soils. All soils showed very large effect sizes following a logarithmic decay relationship
338 with %biochar. This was partly reflected in the infiltration data (minidisc infiltrometer) where the power
339 decay was less clear for the sandy loam soils, while for the SCL-H it was linear and with substantially larger
340 effect sizes at 6% and 10% biochar than the sandy loam soils. Possibly, the discrepancy between the time
341 to ponding/drainage vs infiltrometer data was caused by the difference in hydraulic conditions during the
342 experiment, i.e. the infiltrometer was used with a constant head while the time to ponding/drainage
343 effectively used a falling head. None of these strong effects on hydrological variables could be explained
344 by observed effects on soil structure variables. The increase in hydraulic conductivity that we observed,
345 however, was several orders of magnitude larger than what Zhou et al. (2018) found. This may have been
346 caused by the relatively coarse particle size of the biochar that we used, i.e. our average biochar particle
347 size was approximately 20 times larger, with 37% > 2 mm. Besides the effect size, the relationships between
348 biochar concentration and the soil hydrology vs soil structure variables were also different, i.e. logarithmic
349 decay relationships for the former and mostly linear relationships for the latter. The exception to this are
350 the biochar dose responses of MWD for the two sandy loam soils, which followed a second order
351 polynomial relationship. The different types of biochar dose response curves for the structural vs the

352 hydrological indicators, suggests that soil structural changes occurred other than BD changes, which caused
353 the large effects on soil hydrology, i.e. soil slumping leading to hardset soil. However, the direct indicator
354 of soil hardness showed a linear biochar dose response. It is possible that the coarse nature of the biochar
355 improved hydraulic conductivity drastically, as can be seen in Figures 1a-c, by creating macropores
356 between it and the soil matrix, and that the soil in between the coarse biochar particles was only moderately
357 reduced in hardsetting, as can be seen in Figure 2E. These potential mechanisms require further research to
358 unravel.

359 The SAR values of the soils without biochar reflect the soil properties and climate of the field sites. The
360 SL-H soil developed in a colder and wetter climate than the other two soils (Table 1). Biochar did not affect
361 the SAR of the two sandy loam soils, which indicates that it was not dispersive processes that caused the
362 decrease in MWD for these soils. SAR linearly decreased with %biochar for the SCL-H soil, which is more
363 susceptible to dispersion based on its higher clay content (Table 1). The SAR data also did not indicate
364 dispersive processes. It should be noted that the MWD results are from dry sieving of the incubated soil,
365 not from wet sieving, due to lack of remaining soil sample, which could have provided insights into biochar
366 causing aggregate dispersion. However, all the recorded SAR values are substantially below the threshold
367 for dispersive soils (SAR>10; Huber et al. 2008)

368 Penetration resistance is the most commonly used direct measurement of hardsetting, and although we did
369 observe a decrease with increasing biochar%, the observed pattern does not follow that of the hydrological
370 variables. It needs to be noted, however, that the pocket penetrometer that was used only inserts 2 cm into
371 the soil and is more suitable for crusting than slumping studies. Therefore, PR probes that measure the
372 whole soil depth are recommended for future studies on the effect of biochar on hardsetting. Combined,
373 these results indicate that indirect hardsetting indicators such as time to ponding/drainage may be the most
374 robust and/or sensitive method to measure hardsetting. This suggests that for field studies, weighing
375 lysimeters or double ring infiltrometers may be most suited to monitor hardsetting, perhaps even over the
376 standard direct measurement of PR.

377 From a practical viewpoint, the findings suggest that for the soil sponge function, the optimum biochar
378 loading capacity (Verheijen et al. 2010) may be 1.5% for the SCL-H and 3% for the sandy loam soils,
379 because at those concentrations >90% of the hydrological benefit has been achieved, making higher biochar
380 concentrations economically unviable. However, for the soil habitat function, a higher biochar

381 concentration may be optimal since penetration resistance continued to decrease linearly up to 10% biochar.
382 Reduced soil hardness allows roots to grow deeper, which can impact plant growth and yield (Unkovich et
383 al. 2023), particularly for weaker rooting crops, with deeper rooting potentially also making more water
384 available during dry periods (interaction with the sponge function). Reduced soil hardness also allows soil-
385 nesting pollinators to build their nests, or to exert less energy building their nests (Antoine and Forrest,
386 2021). The optimum biochar dose, therefore, depends on the crop type, water balance, and crop pollination
387 needs for any given field.

388 Unkovich et al. (2023) argue that in “high strength soil”, i.e. vulnerable to hardsetting, a penetrometer
389 should be used because it “[...] despite imperfections, provides approximate benchmarks” This study’s
390 findings, however, suggest that soil hydrological indicators - e.g. here the time to ponding/drainage, in the
391 field possibly a double ring infiltrometer - may be more suitable to measure or monitor, because it was
392 observed to have larger effect sizes than any of the measured soil structural indicators, including penetration
393 resistance.

394 The main limitations of this study are the lack of soil compression, e.g. simulation of soil loading
395 underneath the hoof of a cow, and the short duration of the column experiment relative to field conditions.
396 Further research that focuses on these factors seems justified, based on the large effect sizes on soil
397 hydrology observed. Furthermore, this study strongly suggests that a form of slumping caused the outsized
398 hydrology effects for the observed moderate soil structure effects. Micromorphology, or tomography, or
399 other imaging studies are needed to find direct evidence for which type of slumping as the causative process.
400 The four strong drying-wetting cycles were useful to show that a simple laboratory MWHC analysis is not
401 representative and at least 3 wetting-drying cycles are needed before MWHC stabilizes, but long-term
402 effects on hydraulic properties will likely vary (Jiang et al. 2025).

403 **5. Conclusions**

404 Biochar amendment was found to improve soil hydrology up to several times more strongly than soil
405 structure variables. Although this study did not find direct evidence of slumping, it strongly suggests that
406 biochar amendment can substantially reduce slumping in soils vulnerable to hardsetting, with very large
407 improvements in soil hydrology as a result. These findings suggest that biochar amendment to soils that are
408 vulnerable to hardsetting may be a viable management option to improve both the soil sponge and habitat
409 functions.

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554 b. Conflicts of interest/Competing interests

555 On behalf of all authors, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest.

556 c. Availability of data and material (data transparency)

557 All data will be made publicly available.

558 **Tables**

559 **Table 1.** Main soil and site characteristics. The soils are ordered by decreasing vulnerability to hardsetting.

560 SL-L = Sandy Loam Low organic matter; SL-H = Sandy Loam High organic matter; SCL-H = Sandy Clay
 561 Loam High organic matter.

Soil	Vulnerability to hardsetting	Precipitation (mm)	Temperature (°C)	Altitude (m)	Texture	Particle Size Distribution sand:silt:clay	SOM (%)	pH	EC (mS cm ⁻¹)
SL-L	Very high	500–600	16.5	190	Sandy loam	70:17:13	2.9	5.5	50.0
SL-H	High	800–1000	12.6	441	Sandy loam	70:13:17	4.5	5.6	76.9
SCL-H	Low	600–800	16.5	330	Sandy clay loam	56:19:25	5.4	6.0	135.5

562 **Figure Captions**

563 **Fig. 1** Hydraulic behavior of three pasture soils. Panel (a) shows the time to drainage and panel (b) the time
 564 to saturation, both recorded during the third saturation and drainage cycle. Panel (c) presents unsaturated

565 hydraulic conductivity (K) measured at the beginning of the first saturation cycle; Panels (d), (e), and (f)
566 display the maximum water holding capacity (MWHC) across four consecutive wetting and drainage
567 cycles. Error bars represent standard deviations. Asterisks in Panels (a) and (b) indicate cases where
568 saturation or drainage extended overnight, and minimum values were used

569

570 **Fig. 2** Indicators of soil structure across three pasture soils. Panel (a) presents the mean weight diameter
571 (MWD); Panel (b) displays the weight of the microaggregate fraction in percentage, the asterisk signals a
572 value obtained for the 3% treatment where the soils incubation was not performed at the beginning of the
573 experiment; Panel (c) shows the Sodium Adsorption Ratio (SAR); Panel (d) shows dry bulk density at
574 cycle 1 (BDc1) and cycle 4 (BDc4); Panel (e) presents penetration resistance (PR); and Panel (f)
575 represents a regression between PR and BDc4. Error bars represent standard deviations for each treatment
576 and soil. Asterisk in Panel (b) indicates a mixture that was not incubated